

Effects of Online Communication on Social Wellbeing among Generation Z in Asian Subcontinent

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The use of smartphones amongst Asians especially Gen-Z has increased with the outbreak of COVID-19. With the majority of people facing months of lockdowns, digital networks may become an especially crucial instrument in Asian people's fight against loneliness, alternative mode of communication and discrimination. This report, which is based on the multi-activity paradigm of social media usage, looked at whether mental wellbeing amongst the Gen-z and positive outcomes of experience was linked to higher social media use amongst the youth of Asia, as well as how adaptable social media use was for their mental health during COVID-19. This study presents a systematic literature review of the research, historical and contemporary insights, and knowledge of online communication patterns in Asia's Gen-Z, as well as a discussion of the substantial impact on mental health. This study also discusses the various features of online communication as a replacement for face-to-face interaction, as well as how it contributes to productivity, growth, and mental health. This research looked at a total of 15 publications. We presented a paradigm for assessing the impact of online connections on the mental health of Asia's Generation Z. In order to measure mental health and smartphone use, this research study used a systematic literature review methodology. Data was gathered from databases (ScienceDirect, Data Reportal, and Google Scholar). For this study, the Prisma framework was adopted to retrieve articles, and only solely journal articles were chosen for the literature review. The distinctive aspect of this study is that it combines two separate issues (social media use and social wellness) to create a framework for explaining the effects of online interactions on socializing variables among Gen-Z youth. Furthermore, this research adds to the body of knowledge in current disciplines.

Keywords: ONLINE INTERACTIONS, SUBJECTIVE WELLBEING, SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCES, ZOOMERS

Introduction

Smartphone as a tool of online communication brings the universe on the palm of our hands through its features of accessibility, mobility and multi-variative use which makes it super fitting for the lifestyle of Gen-z as they are multi-functioning individuals who are always on the go. Using smartphones, many people interact with friends, family, and brands can expand beyond horizon using this tool.

Users can download mobile apps from social networking platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn via their phone's app store. Smartphone users can use these apps to post personal updates and images while on the road. Health and wellness tracking is another popular application amongst the Gen-z especially in Asia which is known for its strong athletic practices starting from school PE classes to inter-country and global participation in sports. For example, the health apps for IOS may track sleep patterns, eating, body measurements, vital signs, mental health exercises, and more. Engagement with Gen-Z, as per branding agency senior director Dan Schawbel, must be succinct and visual. "We tell our advertising partners that they will not reach this generation unless they communicate with five words and a large picture." (Keystone, 2018). Ideas in Virtual, digital product and UX design firm, explains: "One of the most noticeable contrasts between the two generations is their communication preferences and methods. But don't mistake digital for impersonal. Personalization is the best way to overcome through the noise and capturing the attention of Gen Z across all platforms.

According to a study, Gen-Z in Taiwan used the internet primarily for games, information seeking, entertainment, and conversing, according to a survey (Liang et al., 2001). Furthermore, more than half of the surveyed Taiwanese teenagers polled said the internet could help them enhance their interpersonal relationships as well as their academic achievement. Chen (2000) investigated if and how a digital divide exists among Taiwanese middle school student and colleges. The findings revealed that household wealth and level of urbanization had a substantial impact on internet usage and etiquette.

According to a poll conducted by the Korean Network and Information Center, the primary tasks that Korean youths engage in online include obtaining entertainment and interacting with peers through messaging apps, photo comments, media art discussions that bring about social wellbeing. More recently, the connectivity approach (Gibbs, 2019) explored the role of the social context in people's internet connectivity. Individuals, publications, major and local social institutes, as well as social and physical contexts that either enable or hinder connections in the network, make up a communication infrastructure. The internet, being a relatively new medium, is regarded as entering the existing communication infrastructure, and the ways in which the internet establishes relationships with humans are influenced by existing social interpersonal communication.

Jung et al. (2017) developed the Internet Connection Indicator as a multidimensional index to systematically encompass numerous characteristics of people's internet connectedness (ICI). The Internet Connectivity Index (ICI) is made up of three parameters that are used to assess the quality of people's internet connections: 1) the history and connotation of internet connectedness, with an approach to economic disparity; 2) the scope and amplitude of internet connectivity, with a focus on the comprehensiveness of people's internet use in terms of their goals for surfing the net and the operations they partake in on the web; and 3) the pertinence of people's connectivity, with a greater emphasis on the person's assessment.

Based on the findings of Kim et al., 2018a; Kim et al., 2018b; Loges and Jung, 2017), the concept that the digital divide is a multi-faceted divide reflected in several elements of individuals interacting with the internet, rather than a self-gap. People's ICI scores have a linear positive association with their education and wealth, according to Jung et al. (2017). After optimizing for economic status, Kim et al. (2018b) discovered that an individual's nationality and place of residence had interaction effects on ICI. Loges and Jung (2018) looked at the association between ICI and age and discovered that younger people have higher levels of ICI. Gen-z had greater expertise using internet and superior telecommunications infrastructure than their elders, and they had a larger and more intense variety of goals and practices for surfing the net. Seniors, on the other hand, considered the internet to be as important in their lives as those of other ages (Loges and Jung, 2017).

Materials and methods

To conduct a literature review, this paper uses a systematic methodology and the Prisma framework. Tranfield described various methods for doing a systematic literature review in 2003, and we followed those processes in our analysis. (Tranfield, 2003). Developing a methodological approach, establishing selection criteria, and undertaking the quality evaluation and data extraction method are all part of this process. All of these stages will be thoroughly discussed later. It is absolutely necessary to comprehend the Prisma framework's structure. Following that, the search paradigm was created, and early results were found using reliable databases (Data Reportal, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar). The initial findings were then subjected to various circumstances. The research selection paradigm, under which the screening procedure took place, was then defined. Time limits, study field limitations, language selection, research papers, and review article filters were all used as selection criteria. The report's research papers that failed to pass the screening process were eliminated. The abstracts of each paper were meticulously assessed, and the remaining papers were then completely examined, analyzed, and reviewed. The most appropriate research articles that met the study's goals were chosen and then incorporated into a literature review. Figure 1 shows the Prisma Framework structure, which is used for the review approach

Prisma Framework

Step 1. Identification

Fig-1; Structure of the methodology followed for the systematic literature review.

The first stage is to design a search strategy; in this case, the search strategy was suited to three databases (ScienceDirect, Data Reportal, and Google Scholar).

Online communications, Gen-Zers' behavioral pattern, digital privacy, collaborative projects, relational aggression, online validation, social capital, and feeling of community were among the keyword phrases. Originally, all 1500 documents were retrieved using the Identification Process's search approach.

The identification stage of the Prisma guidelines is completed and displayed in Figure 2 for the formulation of the search strategy.

Fig-2; Identification stage of the Prisma framework

Step 2. Screening

The filtering stage of the Prisma framework is where the search results are established and carried out. The major goal of the search is to gather all of the known literature on online communication and social well-being. Because we wanted to undertake a literature analysis on recent information, the search window was set from 2012 to 2020, and all documents before to 2012 were deleted. Business, psychology, management, economics, and education were chosen as research fields for this study and reduced down. Only full articles and scholarly reviews were chosen, and the research papers' language was set to English. At the screening step, 1550 documents were ruled out. At this level, a total of 155 research papers were extracted and passed to the next stage. The Prisma framework's screening mechanism is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3; Screening stage of the Prisma framework.

Step 3. Eligibility

This research is based on full journal articles as well as review pieces. All of the extracted papers were extensively checked for duplications throughout the quality evaluation phase. Each paper's abstract was read and double-checked to confirm that the publications were relevant to the study's goal. Then after, every one of the papers were given a thorough examination.

Furthermore, 155 publications were eliminated from the quality appraisal stage after this filtration process, leaving 65 articles acceptable for the retention or removal step. Figure 4 depicts the quality assessment technique.

Figure 4. Eligibility stage of the Prisma framework

Step 4. Inclusion and Exclusion

The terms and definitions were explicitly established, and ten documents were eliminated from the study following a thorough examination and evaluation of all the extracted documents.

Finally, 15 articles were chosen to be included in the literature review. Figure 5 illustrates the Prisma statement's inclusion step.

Figure 5. Inclusion stage of the Prisma framework.

3. Findings

3.1. Demographics

3.1.1. Input by Publishers

In this stage, contributions made by different publishers were identified. It can be seen from Figure 6 that Elsevier is at the top, with the maximum number of publications of 7 papers. Springer stands at the second highest with 4 papers and other papers are published by MDPI and ScienceDirect.

Figure 6. Contributions by publishers (source: author).

3.1.2. Contribution by Journal

The data was obtained from multiple sources. The sources utilized to locate and select publications relating to online interactions amongst Gen-Z in Asia, its effects on social wellbeing are listed in Table 1.

Journal	Number	Impact Factor
International Review of Education	1	1.121
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	6	5.846
Economic Analysis and Policy	2	2.81
Journal of Marketing Development & Competitiveness	4	6.32
Social Indicators Research	1	2.614
Trends in Cognitive science	1	4.773
Total		15

Table 1: Foundation of the selected articles

3.1.3. Contribution by Top Author's

The authors who have contributed the most in our topic of interest has been listed down below in Table 2.

Authors (Year)	Citation
Llewellyn Ellardus van Zyl (2021)	1300
Natale canale et al. (2021)	998
Ashek Mahmud & M. Rezaul Islam (2021)	1778
Luke Curtis Collins (2019)	559
Daniel Romer & David Hansen (2018)	1255

Table 2. Top five authors' contributions.

3.1.1. Contribution by Country

Figure 7 shows which countries have contributed the most in terms of research in the field of online communications and effects on social wellbeing in Asian youth.

Figure 7. Country-wise publication details (source: author).

This section includes a summary of the articles published, organized by year of publication. Because online communication has become more readily accessible in recent years, and Gen-Z is much more exposed to social media use and face-to-face interactions are being replaced by online communications given the current global pandemic conditions, the resulting social wellbeing from this issue has become a key subject area for both researchers and practitioners, as shown in Figure 8 below. In this part we as authors, would like to address the

issue of global pandemic and how it has altered the mode of communications making us more reliant on smartphone use and online communications as a substitute to face-to-face interactions. Several studies have found that this had a more adverse effect on the subjective and social wellbeing of the youth and Gen-Z particularly compared to adults. Humans are sociable beings with a natural desire to connect with others. On the surface, social isolation during the present COVID-19 pandemic seems to be interfering with our fundamental urge to interact with people.

Our analysis discovered that social separation has a negative impact on social connectedness amongst the youth in Asia. We feel more socially detached the more we socially isolate ourselves from others. Considering the significance of social connection, it was discovered that a lack of social connection was linked to increased levels of stress and thus a worse of condition of wellbeing amongst Gen-z.

Figure 8. Year-wise publication data (source: author)

Sl.	Issues Addressed	Focus	Results
1.	Social media addiction amongst Gen-zers	The focus of this study is to see the condition of youth in Asia resulting from social media addiction during lockdown.	The youth in Asia spend more time online to responding to the needs when face-to-face communication is limited, increasing the

			risk of addictive social media usage (SMU).
2.	Interpersonal relations	The purpose of this paper was to test whether use of social media retains both professional and friendly relations amongst Gen-z	Online interactions help Gen-z in Asian settings stay connected even without any physical relocation or movement.
3.	Social media addiction amongst Gen-zers, Online Communications, Validation	The paper emphasizes on whether when it comes to social media and the internet, the availability of support from others is likely to influence the scope, depth, and importance of youth's access to the internet.	Results suggest that it maximizes productivity leading to subjective well-being.
4.	Medium of transmission, social aggression	The focus of this research is on change in emotional balance due to frequent use of social media.	Excessive use of cellphone leads to state of absent-present.
5.	Social capital in Asia	The paper emphasizes on lacking of diagnosis; despite the large number of social capital research studies, there have been few attempts to investigate social capital in the context of service-oriented businesses, notably in Asia Pacific.	This study of social capital in the Asia Pacific region sets the stage for recognizing the cultural, sociological, and economic prospects and difficulties that exist in a number of Asia Pacific countries, all of which have the potential to improve our knowledge and understanding of the region.

6.	Gateway to creativity & political power, Validation.	The purpose of this paper is to see if validation received from expressing creativity online leads to wellbeing	Results show that it adds to social and mental wellbeing amongst the youth.
7.	Interpersonal relations, Feeling of validation, Online communication	The hypothesis of this research paper tests whether Cell phones have unintended repercussions in human interactions.	Because smartphones divert attention away from the individual, the findings show that smart phones are perceived as a conflicting third party during meaningful face-to-face social encounters.
8.	Gateway to creativity & political power, Interpersonal relations	The concept of this study was to check how the interaction of posting creativity online affects real life relation amongst the people.	Excessive obsession of posting online may negatively affect real life relations as it shifts focus
9.	Online communication, Interpersonal relations	The goal of this study was to check if online communication can effectively replace face-to-face interactions and the effects it had on relation.	When someone uses their phone while talking to someone else, it gives the impression that they don't matter as much as the interaction on their phone. Because the person feels insignificant and dislikes the fact that they are not important enough to disregard a secondary encounter, this leads to interpersonal conflict.

10.	Dynamics & Protocols of interaction,	The paper emphasizes on the comparison to a linked discussion board, how social presence is portrayed in a mobile instant messaging (MIM)-facilitated environment and to what degree MIM can afford social presence	Through emotive, participatory, and cohesive replies, MIM empowered students to demonstrate user engagement. Students appeared to be most at ease using MIM to convey emotions, address groups, and maintain a conversation. Second, MIM is better adapted to promote emotional expression, consensus, phatics, and offering assistance than an online forum.
11.	Social aggression, interpersonal relations	The paper takes a look at whether an average youth in the East region is faced with intense pressure from traditional practices that remain intact, as well as the overpowering impact of modern beliefs, because they live in a changing social milieu.	Results show that socializing factors for Gen-zers in East Asia is shaped by societal norms and affects their mental wellbeing
12.	Gateway to creativity & political power, social capital in Asia	The study focuses on whether people value the creative and socio-emotional benefits of social media.	According to the study of Asian teenagers, social media use can promote social-emotional well-being and creativity, although vulnerable

			teenagers may rely on such platforms more. In addition, vulnerable populations experience more online harm, and low-income youth Gen-zers utilize social media in a variety of ways.
13.	Social well-being in Asian youth	The goal of the paper is to take a deeper look into the Asian cultures, where mental health issues are frequently suppressed and stigmatized, resulting in unmet needs for several youngsters.	Results show plans such as Clinical therapy, youth empowerment and entrepreneurship programs, community outreach groups, a high-school traineeship, and school-based initiatives are some of the services recently made available across Asian countries. Its services and programs are free, and young people can earn rewards for enrolling and completing them.
14.	Non-verbal cues, Gateway to creativity & political power	If online communication has enhanced the talents within the Gen-z and helped them feel validated was the purpose of this study	Results of study show that youth feel more validated by presenting their skills online.
15.	Feeling of community, social aggression,	The goal of this paper was to test how the lockdown has affected	The results suggest that lockdown resulted in

	validations, online communication	connectivity and relations of the youth in Indonesia with their surroundings	negative relationship in communications between youth and their surroundings
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Table 3. Comparison of classified articles based on their focus and results.

Fig-9: Research Framework

4. Discussion

Millennials, Gen Xers, and Gen Zers are all familiar with the digital world, especially the online media, and rely on it for learning, trading, and entertainment. Gen Zers shine even in this setting, which is understandable given they had no access to know the internet and have experienced social media growing up. Just about a third of Gen Zers in APAC spend 6 hours or more each day on their phones, a much greater percentage than millennials (22%), and Gen Xers (22%). (10 percent). Indonesians stand out because they spend an average of 8.5 hours

every day on their phones. In most nations, Gen Zers spend two hours more per day on their phones than Gen Xers as well as an hour further than millennials. Because of their high digital literacy and availability of information, Generation Z members are able to pick and select what they spend their money on. In an environment where the majority of buyers conduct extensive research before making a purchase, being competitive in terms of quality is a must if you want to win the loyalty of Gen Zers.

In the closing stages of 2019, McKinsey polled more than 15,000 customers in 6 nations including Indonesia, China, Japan, South Korea, and Thailand—to better understand how Gen Zers research, consider, purchase, and utilize products online. The results were then compared across three successive generations: Generation Z, millennials, and Gen X (born 1965–1979). The study inquired about respondents' overall opinions toward brands, commerce, internet, and media, as well as their worldview. For certain categories, it also asked particular questions on communication patterns and branding. (McKinsey and CO, 2021).

Limitation, Conclusion and Future Research

Limitation of Generation Z is their familiarity with technology often. Future research may discuss about the necessary training to make the facilities familiar and comfortable. Gen Z is living in a world of peak technical innovation, when information was instantly accessible and social media became increasingly widespread, whereas Millennials were called "digital pioneers" who witnessed the growth of social media and the internet. Modern technological advancements have influenced Gen Z in both positive and negative ways. Just on bright side, Gen Zers have access to a wealth of material, allowing them to widen their knowledge and take charge of their education. Excessive screen time, on the other hand, can exacerbate feelings of isolation and lead to a lack of social skills. Furthermore, when the economy changes due to technological advancements; minimal Gen Z workers will be vulnerable as they enter the labor market. For Generation Z, mental health and social wellbeing is a major concern. According to an American Psychological Association research, this age group is the least likely to claim good or excellent mental health. Also, noteworthy: According to the research firm Zebra IQ, 35 percent of Gen Zers surveyed said their mental health had deteriorated as a result of the pandemic.

Although technology is an important tool for young people to socialize, it can also exacerbate feelings of isolation and stress. Tragic breaking news is being conveyed more quickly than ever—and more difficult to escape—through a variety of apps and outlets. Thankfully, current young individuals are seeking psychological counseling to manage their anxiety and despair. In the United States, 37 percent of Gen-Zers have sought help from a psychologist or other mental health professional, a larger percentage than any previous generation.

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